

Cognitive edge-cloud with serverless computing

Welcome to our 7th Newsletter!

As we continue our journey, we are excited to share the progress made over the last three months, even during the summer season. Despite the holidays, the dedication of our team has allowed us to maintain momentum and achieve significant advancements in the project.

In this edition, you will find:

- **Summer Achievements:** Discover the exciting milestones we reached over the summer months, keeping the pace of innovation high.
- **Events:** Learn about the events we have participated in, sharing knowledge and collaborating with key industry players.
- **Publications:** Catch up on the latest submissions and publications.

We hope you enjoy reading this update and encourage you to stay connected for more exciting news ahead!

Our Latest Highlights

EDGELESS at The Nordic Connection Retreat

On August 31 and September 1, 2024, the **EDGELESS** team had the privilege of participating in a talk and discussion at **The Nordic Connection Retreat**, held in Icking, Germany. Organized by our partner, the **Technical University of Munich**.

EDGELESS at the 4th CyberHOT hands-on cybersecurity Summer School

On September 9-10, 2024, the **CyberHOT Summer School** took place in Piraeus, Greece, offering a hands-on cybersecurity training program aimed at boosting technical capabilities in cybersecurity. Attended by participants from around the world, including key members of the **EDGELESS** project from the **Technical University of Crete**.

Explore Our Zenodo Community

Discover the newest publications and deliverables from the EDGELESS project on our Zenodo account!

“EDGELESS: A Software Architecture for Stateful FaaS at the Edge”

“Abandon All Hope Ye Who Enter Here: A Dynamic, Longitudinal Investigation of Android’s Data Safety Section”

“Dynamic Frequency-Based Side-Channel Attacks against Modern Sandbox Environments”

“Energy-Efficient Deployment of Stateful FaaS Vertical Applications on Edge Data Networks”

“Ambusher: Exploring the Security of Distributed SDN Controllers through Protocol State Fuzzing”

“SecureExecutor: An Automated Way to Leverage SCONE to Enhance Application Security”

“Rethinking the mobile edge for vehicular services”

with more to come soon

Our Latest Articles

Smart City Use Case Blog Article #2

The Smart City Surveillance UC intends to detect dangerous situations, such as road accidents and other harmful events, triggering the necessary teams and authorities, with the goal of decreasing the response time from first responders.

OPA inside EDGELESS for SLAs

The EDGELESS ecosystem combines the Lambda architecture with the Edge-cloud continuum vision by providing a platform to run on-demand computational processes packaged as functions either close to the data source or inside clouds for efficiency.

SEATED 2024: workshop on serverless at the edge sponsored by EDGELESS and located with ACM HPDC

The 1st workshop on Serverless at the Edge (SEATED) was held on June 3rd, 2024, co-located with the ACM Conference on High Performance and Distributed Computing (HPDC).

CONSORTIUM

The project unites **12 partners** from **6 European countries**, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

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